

Notes

Physico-chemical Studies of Zirconyl Molybdate Complex

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SOME precipitation complexes have been studied spectrophotometrically by Joshi and Bhargava¹ and conductometrically by Sahu². In the present investigation authors have taken up the stoichiometric, solubility, thermal stability and gravimetric study of zirconyl molybdate complex.

B. D. H. make zirconyl chloride and E. Merck sodium molybdate were used. Preparation of solutions and their dilution were done with double distilled water. Resistance of solutions were measured with "RADART R. C. Bridge, type 432A" with dip type conductivity cell.

Stoichiometry: The complex was first studied by monovariation method³. $1 \times 10^{-2} M$ and $8 \times 10^{-3} M$ equimolar solutions were used. In one set the volume of zirconyl chloride was kept constant (10 ml) while in a second set that of sodium molybdate. The total volume in both the sets was maintained to 40 ml. The volume of added reagent when plotted against the observed conductance gives significant breaks at 10 ml of the reagent, confirming 1:1 complex formation (Fig.).

Preparation: 10 ml each of *N*/10 Zirconyl chloride and *N*/10 sodium molybdate were mixed and allowed to attain the equilibrium, when curdy white precipitate settled down leaving the clear supernatant liquid. The precipitate was filtered through a silica bed funnel washed with water, for complete removal of chloride ions, dried at 105°-110° in an air oven for about 15 hr and cooled and analysed.

Analysis: A small weighed quantity of the substance was taken Molybdenum was estimated as lead molybdate⁴ and zirconyl as pyrophosphate⁵.

Results

Found Zirconium 32.26, Mo 30.30, Req'd for $\text{ZrOMoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$: Zr 31.65, Mo, 30.87.

Solubility: The solubility of the complex was determined by preparing a saturated solution at 30° 10 ml of this solution was taken in a cleaned and weighed 50 ml beaker and allowed for slow evaporation. The weight of the residue was to be 0.0026 gm. The solubility of Zirconyl molybdate at 30° is therefore 0.026 percent w/v.

Thermal Stability: The complex in the fine powder form is first heated for some time at 105°-110° to eliminate any absorbed atmospheric moisture. 2.0 g of it was taken in a weighed silica crucible and heated in a muffle furnace. Observations were made by heating the sample for one hour at every 20° rise of temperature. The original colour of the complex was pale yellow. No change in colour and weight was observed till 450°. At 500° the colour of the complex changed to grey with a greenish ting. At the same temperature the loss in weight was recorded to be 0.24 g which corresponds to two water molecules (theoretical loss should be 0.238 gm.). The sample was continued further heating for fusion but it did not fuse even up to 1000°.

Acknowledgement

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References

1. JOSHI & BHARGAVA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 40, 19.
2. K. N. SAHU, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 44, 221.
3. I. A. KHAN and D. SEN, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1956, 49A, 226.
4. F. P. TREADWELL, and W. T. HALL, *Analytical Chemistry*, 1963, Vol II, p. 116.
5. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text book of quantitative analysis", 1953 ed. p. 476.